

Some Mathematical Properties and Formulas in Mechanical Tensors and in 1st and 3rd Isotropic Invariants in General or in the Case of Triangular Cauchy-Green Tensors on $GL^+(n)$

Jérémie Gaston Sambou ✉

Laboratory of Mathematics and Applications,
University Assane Seck of Ziguinchor, Senegal

Edouard Diouf

Laboratory of Mathematics and Applications,
University Assane Seck of Ziguinchor, Senegal

Article History:

Received: 30.06.2025 Revised: 18.07.2025 Accepted: 21.07.2025 Published: 27.07.2025

ABSTRACT:

In this research paper, we have proposed as a work to elaborate some properties and formulas very useful for a better comprehension of mechanical tensors for beginning researchers in mechanics and any interested mathematician reader. We show that most of the tensors used in mechanics are symmetrical and that the two Cauchy-Green tensors are identical in planar transformation. In the results, after showing the membership of Cauchy-Green tensors for incompressible deformations and the membership of deformation gradient tensor for that these Cauchy-Green tensors to be equal to Identity tensor, we found two important formulas in the calculation of the first elementary isotropic invariant in general case but also the calculation of the third elementary isotropic invariant in the case of triangular Cauchy-Green tensor and all that in any finite dimension ($n < 1$).

Keywords: deformation gradient tensors, Cauchy-Green tensors, Triangular matrices, isotropic elementary invariants, Incompressible deformation.

Suggested Citation: J.G. Sambou, E. Diouf, "Some Mathematical Properties and Formulas in Mechanical Tensors and in 1st and 3rd Isotropic Invariants in General or in the Case of Triangular Cauchy-Green Tensors on $GL^+(n)$," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3(4), pp. 108-116, Jul-Aug 2025. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2025.3(4).11

INTRODUCTION

In mathematics, more precisely in multilinear algebra and in differential geometry, a tensor designates a very general object, the value of which is expressed in a vector space. It can be used, among other things, to represent multilinear or multivector applications. However in mechanics and physics, tensors are used to describe and manipulate various quantities and physical properties such as the electric field, permittivity, deformations, or even stresses [1].

Continuum mechanics, the deformation gradient, Cauchy-Green tensors and Cauchy stress tensor allow to study the strain rates and the reaction of the material when it is subjected to forces which transform it and certain conditions of rank one convexity, polyconvexity and ellipticity of energy functions of deformation [2, 3].

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

For an isotropic and compressible material, a study shows that the loss of ellipticity criterion depends on the determinant of the Hessian matrix of the energy potential and therefore of the invariants of the Cauchy Green tensor [4]. Thus, the absence of a stability criterion may lead to comparing the ellipticity condition considered as a local stability criterion to the local form of classical stability analysis by the Lyapunov theorem [5].

Others criterias such as rank 1 convexity and polyconvexity are properties that play an important role in the nonlinear theory of hyperelasticity. The notion of polyconvexity was introduced into the context of nonlinear elasticity theory by John Ball [6].

A study shows that the rank 1 convexity implies the polyconvexity of a strain energy function in case of a planar deformation, that means a two dimension deformation [7].

Another study goes further by showing an equivalence between the rank 1 convexity and the polyconvexity of a strain energy function in three dimension deformation [8].

In this paper, we first work in the definitions of some tensors using in mechanic and in some groups in which those tensors belong. We secondly did a mathematical formulation where we state and demonstrate important properties on these mechanical tensors.

The formulation allow us to elaborate two important results in the calculation of the first and third elementaries isotropic invariant respectively in general and in the case of triangular Cauchy-Green tensor in any finite dimension ($n < 1$).

PRELIMINARIES

Definitions 1

Matrices are arrays of elements (numbers, characters) which are used to interpret in computational terms, and therefore operational, the theoretical results of linear algebra and even bilinear algebra.

A matrix with m rows and n columns is a rectangular array of $m \times n$ numbers, arranged row by row. There are m rows, and in each row n . A matrix for which the number m of rows is equal to the number n of columns will be called a square matrix of size (or order) n . elements.

A triangular matrix is a square matrix of which a triangular part of the values, delimited by the principal diagonal, is zero. According to this previous definition, we can see that there can be two kinds of

triangular matrices: An upper triangular matrix with coefficients in \mathbb{R} is a square matrix with coefficients in whose values under the principal diagonal are zero, means:

$$\mathbf{F} = (F_{i,j}) \text{ is an upper triangular matrix if and only if } F_{i,j} = 0 \forall i > j$$

A lower triangular matrix with coefficients in \mathbb{R} is a square matrix with coefficients in \mathbb{R} whose values above the main diagonal are zero, means:

$$\mathbf{F} = (F_{i,j}) \text{ is a lower triangular matrix if and only if } F_{i,j} = 0 \forall i < j$$

A diagonal matrix with coefficients in \mathbb{R} is a square matrix with coefficients in \mathbb{R} whose values above and under the main diagonal are zero, means:

$$\mathbf{F} = (F_{i,j}) \text{ is a diagonal matrix if and only if } F_{i,j} = 0 \forall i \neq j$$

The determinant of a triangular matrix is equal to the product of the terms of the main diagonal:

$$\mathbf{F} = (F_{i,j}) \text{ is a triangular matrix, then } \det(\mathbf{F}) = \prod_{k=1}^n F_{kk}$$

Let \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} be two matrices satisfying the multiplicity condition; we mean the product $\mathbf{A} \times \mathbf{B}$ is defined. Then the determinant of this product is equal to the product of the two determinants.

$$\det(\mathbf{A} \times \mathbf{B}) = \det(\mathbf{A}) \times \det(\mathbf{B})$$

Let n be a strictly positive integer and \mathbf{A} a square matrix of order n . We say that \mathbf{A} is symmetric if for all $i, j = 1, \dots, n$, its order coefficients a_{ij} and a_{ji} are equal, this which is equivalent to saying that \mathbf{A} is equal to its transpose.

Definitions 2

Let's consider here the group $GL^+(n)$, which represents the set of matrices defined by:

$$GL^+(n) = \{\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n / \det(\mathbf{F}) > 0\} \quad (1)$$

and his subset $SL^+(n)$ defined by:

$$SL^+(n) = \{\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n / \det(\mathbf{F}) = 1\} \quad (2)$$

There is also the orthogonal group $O(n)$ which represents the set of matrices defined by:

$$O(n) = \{\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n / \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{1}\} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ is the identity tensor.

We can see here that the $SL^+(n)$ group represents the set of Cauchy-Green tensors in incompressible.

MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

Let's consider a continuous system where a material point occupies the position $\mathbf{X} = (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n)$ before the deformation and the position $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ after deformation, where x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are function of \mathbf{X} , we mean defined by the following kinematics:

$$x_1 = x_1(\mathbf{X}); x_2 = x_2(\mathbf{X}); \dots; x_n = x_n(\mathbf{X}) \quad (4)$$

To describe the local deformation, we use the deformation gradient tensor noted \mathbf{F} which is also called the tangent linear application. This tensor allow to have the volume change from his determinant which is always positive, so that:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial x_1}{\partial X_1} & \frac{\partial x_1}{\partial X_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial x_1}{\partial X_n} \\ \frac{\partial x_2}{\partial X_1} & \frac{\partial x_2}{\partial X_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial x_2}{\partial X_n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \frac{\partial x_n}{\partial X_1} & \frac{\partial x_n}{\partial X_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial x_n}{\partial X_n} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

In continuum mechanics, it is important to specify that from the deformation gradient tensor \mathbf{F} , We can measure the strain rate by calculating the familiar tensors that are: right Cauchy-Green tensor in Lagrangian configuration which is noted \mathbf{C} and left Cauchy-Green tensor in Eulerian configuration which is noted \mathbf{B} , with:

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F}; \quad \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^T \quad (6)$$

It should be noted that these two tensors although they differ by their formula describe the study in an equivalent way.

These Cauchy-Green tensors have adjoints tensors which are noted \mathbf{C}^* and \mathbf{B}^* defined by:

$$\mathbf{C}^* = \det(\mathbf{C}) \mathbf{C}^{-1}; \quad \mathbf{B}^* = \det(\mathbf{B}) \mathbf{B}^{-1} \quad (7)$$

In isotropic deformation, we can calculate the three first elementary invariants which are:

$$I_1 = \text{tr}(\mathbf{C}) = \text{tr}(\mathbf{B}); \quad I_2 = \text{tr}(\mathbf{C}^*) = \text{tr}(\mathbf{B}^*); \quad I_3 = \det(\mathbf{C}) = \det(\mathbf{B}) \quad (8)$$

In mechanics, a strain is said to be incompressible if the third isotropic invariant is equal to 1.

$$I_3 = 1 \quad (9)$$

These previous mathematical tensors play a very important role in mechanics and engineering. However to study the reaction of the material when it is subjected to deformation caused by forces, One introduces the Cauchy-stress tensor defined in isotropic case [10,11] by:

$$\mathbf{T} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{I_3}} [W_1 \mathbf{B} + (I_2 W_2 + I_3 W_3) \mathbf{1} - I_3 W_2 \mathbf{B}^{-1}] \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ represents the identity tensor and the $W_i (i = 1, 2, 3)$ are given by $W_i = \partial W / \partial I_i$ with W an energy function of deformation.

It is also necessary to specify that with the hypothesis of the absence of volume forces, the equilibrium equations are summarized as:

$$\operatorname{div}(\mathbf{T}) = 0 \quad (11)$$

Properties 1

- 1-Cauchy-Green tensors \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{B} are always symmetrical.
- 2-The inverse of a symmetric matrix is symmetric.
- 3-The adjoint of a symmetric tensor is symmetrical.
- 4-Cauchy-Stress tensor \mathbf{T} is symmetrical.

Proof:

- 1-A tensor of the second order is said to be symmetric if it is equal to its transposed.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C}^T &= (\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F})^T = \mathbf{F}^T (\mathbf{F}^T)^T = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F}, \\ \mathbf{B}^T &= (\mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^T)^T = (\mathbf{F}^T)^T \mathbf{F}^T = \mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^T. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

- 2-Let's \mathbf{D} be the inverse of a symmetric matrix $\mathbf{A} (\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}^T)$.

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{A}\mathbf{D})^T &= (\mathbf{D}\mathbf{A})^T = (\mathbf{I}_d)^T = \mathbf{I}_d; \implies \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{D}^T = \mathbf{D}^T \mathbf{A}^T = \mathbf{I}_d, \\ \mathbf{A}^T &= \mathbf{A}; \implies \mathbf{A} \mathbf{D}^T = \mathbf{D}^T \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}_d \implies \mathbf{D}^T \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}_d \implies \mathbf{D}^T = \mathbf{A}^{-1} = \mathbf{D}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

So $\mathbf{D}^T = \mathbf{D}$, which proves that \mathbf{D} is a symmetric matrix.

- 3-We have:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{C}^*)^T &= (\det(\mathbf{C}) \mathbf{C}^{-1})^T = \det(\mathbf{C}) \mathbf{C}^{-T} = \det(\mathbf{C}) (\mathbf{C}^T)^{-1}; \\ (\mathbf{B}^*)^T &= (\det(\mathbf{B}) \mathbf{B}^{-1})^T = \det(\mathbf{B}) \mathbf{B}^{-T} = \det(\mathbf{C}) (\mathbf{B}^T)^{-1}; \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

And as the transposed of a symmetric tensor and the inverse of a symmetric tensor are symmetrical; then according to the formulas (11), the tensors \mathbf{C}^* and \mathbf{B}^* will be also symmetrical.

- 4-We know that multiplying a symmetric tensor by a scalar will give a symmetric tensor because all components are multiplied by the same scalar. And also the sum of the symmetric tensors gives a symmetric tensor.

\mathbf{T} being the product of a sum of symmetric tensors by a scalar, so \mathbf{T} is a symmetric tensor.

Remark:

In mechanics, the deformation gradient tensor, the Cauchy-Green tensors, their adjoint and the Cauchy stress tensor are always symmetrical.

APPLICATIONS AND RESULTS

Let us now consider the case where the deformation gradient or the tangent linear application obtained is a tensor $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n$ and \mathbf{F}^T is transposed matrix.

So then the Cauchy-Green tensors become:

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{1,i}^T F_{i,1}) & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{1,i}^T F_{i,2}) & \dots & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{1,i}^T F_{i,n}) \\ \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{2,i}^T F_{i,1}) & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{2,i}^T F_{i,2}) & \dots & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{2,i}^T F_{i,n}) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{n,i}^T F_{i,1}) & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{n,i}^T F_{i,2}) & \dots & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{n,i}^T F_{i,n}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

and

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{1,i} F_{i,1}^T) & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{1,i} F_{i,2}^T) & \dots & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{1,i} F_{i,n}^T) \\ \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{2,i} F_{i,1}^T) & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{2,i} F_{i,2}^T) & \dots & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{2,i} F_{i,n}^T) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{n,i} F_{i,1}^T) & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{n,i} F_{i,2}^T) & \dots & \sum_{i=1}^n (F_{n,i} F_{i,n}^T) \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Where $F_{i,j}^T$ are the components of \mathbf{F}^T

From these previous expressions defined in (18) and (19), we can see that even for the case of triangular matrices the Cauchy-Green tensors remain with n^2 non-zero components if the components of the triangle of the deformation gradient are all non-zero. So the triangular property of gradient deformation has no influence in the number of non-zero components of Cauchy-Green tensors.

The influence of the triangular property of Cauchy-Green tensors will be studied in what is coming.

Case of a Planar Kinematics Deformation

Let's consider here the deformation kinematics defined in the plane by:

$$x_1 = x_1(X_1, X_2); \quad x_2 = x_2(X_1, X_2) \quad (17)$$

It follows F given by:

$$F = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_{11} & \lambda_{12} \\ \lambda_{21} & \lambda_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

where $\lambda_{ij} = \partial x_i / \partial X_j$

After calculation of Cauchy-Green tensor, we obtain:

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_{11}^2 + \lambda_{21}^2 & a \\ a & \lambda_{12}^2 + \lambda_{22}^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

and

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_{11}^2 + \lambda_{21}^2 & a \\ a & \lambda_{12}^2 + \lambda_{22}^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

with a defined by $a = \lambda_{11}\lambda_{12} + \lambda_{21}\lambda_{22}$.

Case of a Three-Dimensional Kinematics Deformation

Here the deformation kinematics is defined in the space by:

$$x_1 = x_1(X_1, X_2, X_3); \quad x_2 = x_2(X_1, X_2, X_3); \quad x_3 = x_3(X_1, X_2, X_3) \quad (21)$$

So the gradient deformation \mathbf{F} will be given by:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_{11} & \lambda_{12} & \lambda_{13} \\ \lambda_{21} & \lambda_{22} & \lambda_{23} \\ \lambda_{31} & \lambda_{32} & \lambda_{33} \end{pmatrix} \quad (22)$$

where $\lambda_{ij} = \partial x_i / \partial X_j$ as previously.

Calculation of Cauchy-Green tensor gives us the following expressions:

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_{11}^2 + \lambda_{21}^2 + \lambda_{31}^2 & a_1 & a_2 \\ a_1 & \lambda_{12}^2 + \lambda_{22}^2 + \lambda_{32}^2 & a_3 \\ a_2 & a_3 & \lambda_{13}^2 + \lambda_{23}^2 + \lambda_{33}^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (23)$$

and

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_{11}^2 + \lambda_{21}^2 + \lambda_{31}^2 & b_1 & b_2 \\ b_1 & \lambda_{12}^2 + \lambda_{22}^2 + \lambda_{32}^2 & b_3 \\ b_2 & b_3 & \lambda_{13}^2 + \lambda_{23}^2 + \lambda_{33}^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (24)$$

with a_i and b_j are all function of λ_{ij} .

Remark:

We note that in planar deformation, the two Cauchy-Green tensors \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{B} remain identical.

Results

Properties 2

1-Incompressible deformation is equivalent to \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{B} elements of $SL^+(n)$.

2- $\mathbf{F} \in O(n)$ is equivalent to $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{I}_d$.

3-For any mechanic transformation, $I_1 = \sum_{i,j=1}^n \lambda_{ij}^2$.

4-If \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C} are triangular tensors, then $I_3 = \prod_{j=1}^n (\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_{ij}^2)$.

Proof

1- and 2-

The proofs of 1 and 2 are obtained from the condition of incompressibility, the definitions of the tensors and that of the orthogonal group $O(n)$.

3-Let's $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n$, the matrix product $\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F}$ or $\mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^T$ shows that:

The main component of the first line $\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_{i1}^2$

The main component of the second line is $\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_{i2}^2$

And so on until the main component of the last line which is $\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_{in}^2$

So with the *trace* formula, we obtain $I_1 = \sum_{i,j=1}^n \lambda_{ij}^2$.

4-Let's $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n$, a triangular matrix. In this case, we know that the determinant of \mathbf{B} is equal to the product of its components of the main diagonal, i.e $I_3 = \prod_{i=1}^n B_{ii}$

And as:

$$B_{11} = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_{i1}^2 ;$$

$$B_{22} = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_{i2}^2 ; \text{ and so on until}$$

$$B_{nn} = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_{in}^2 ;$$

$$\text{So then } I_3 = \prod_{i=1}^n (\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_{ij}^2).$$

That what gives the complete proof.

CONCLUSION

In this mathematical research, we have proposed as a work to show certain properties of some mechanical tensors and to elaborate two new formulas in the general and also particular cases of tensors. This study is done on $GL+(n)$.

We have given some definitions on the tensors of order 2 which are at the base of our activity and defined some of their groups.

A kinematic of deformation was given and from it, the deformation gradient tensor, its Cauchy-Green tensors and its isotropic elementary invariants was calculated.

From the calculated expressions, we have shown through a first proposition that in mechanics, the deformation gradient tensor, the Cauchy-Green tensors, their adjoint and the Cauchy stress tensor are always symmetrical.

In the second proposition, we show that incompressible deformation is equivalent to \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{B} elements of $SL+(n)$ and that \mathbf{C} or \mathbf{B} equal to \mathbf{I}_d if and only if \mathbf{F} is an element of $O(n)$.

In this second proposition, two important formulas are found. The first formula allows to calculate I_1 for any \mathbf{C} or \mathbf{B} on $GL+(n)$ and the second allows the calculation of I_3 in the case of triangular Cauchy-Green tensor on $GL+(n)$.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. G. Sambou and E. Diouf, "Analysis of the antiplane shear of certain materials," *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 666–670, Mar. 2018. ISSN 2229-5518.
- [2] G. Aubert, "Necessary and sufficient conditions for isotropic rank-one convex functions in dimension 2," *Journal of Elasticity*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 31–46, Apr. 1995. doi: 10.1007/BF00042440
- [3] B. Dacorogna, "Necessary and sufficient conditions for strong ellipticity of isotropic functions in any dimension," *Discrete and Continuous Dynamical Systems - Series B*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 257–263, 2001. doi: 10.3934/dcdsb.2001.1.257
- [4] E. Diouf, "Sur l'ellipticit des quations non linaires pour une certaine classe de matriau isotrope et compressible," *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 327–334, Oct. 2015. ISSN 2028-9324.

- [5] A. Lyapunov, *The General Problem of the Stability of Motion*, Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, 1992. ISBN 0748400621.
- [6] J. M. Ball, "Convexity conditions and existence theorems in nonlinear elasticity," *Archive for Rational Mechanics and Analysis*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 337–403, 1977. doi: 10.1007/BF00279992
- [7] I. D. Ghiba, R. G. Martin, and P. Neff, "Rank-one convexity implies polyconvexity in isotropic planar incompressible elasticity," *Journal de Mathématiques Pures et Appliquées*, vol. 116, pp. 88–104, 2018. Preprint available at: arXiv:1609.01339.
- [8] J. G. Sambou and E. Diouf, "An equivalence between the rank 1 convexity and polyconvexity of energy functions on $SL^+(3)$," *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology*, vol. 66, no. 9, pp. 17–25, Sep. 2019. doi: 10.14445/22315373/IJMTT-V66I9P504

